

CROWDFUNDING ART PROJECTS: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract: *Crowdfunding is becoming an increasingly prevalent method for financing projects in arts and culture. This phenomenon involves gathering financial resources via the Internet from various donors to support the work of organizations or individuals, enabling the diversification of funding sources and greater community involvement. The research aims to understand the challenges, opportunities, and trends identified through a systematic review of academic literature on financing art projects using the crowdfunding model. This study examined 20 scholarly papers indexed in the Web of Science (WoS) database, including 2 conference papers and 18 papers published in journals. The results indicate that the academic literature on this phenomenon is recent, showing a growing trend in the volume of research. The analyzed studies employed various methodologies, with case studies and both qualitative and quantitative analyses being the most dominant. The contribution of this work can be seen in its systematic review and in-depth analysis of the relevant literature closely related to the crowdfunding model in art. The study has identified the need for further research into specific contexts and local practices in less-researched environments.*

Keywords: *Crowdfunding, art projects, literature review.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Financing creative projects, especially when they are not part of an institutional framework, poses numerous challenges and risks (Rijanto, 2022). Technological advancement, rising digitalization trends, and frequent financial issues require that artists go beyond traditional financing methods (Foà, 2019; Guimarães & Maehle, 2025). By analyzing the positions of artists in times of social and economic instability, such as wars and pandemics, some authors (Kovpak & Lebid, 2022) have identified several principal problems, among which one may single out artist emigration, significant drops of income in the creative sector, and the discontinuation of financial activities. These findings suggest that artistic activity is vulnerable in times of crisis and underline the need to develop sustainable models of art support. Crowdfunding, the practice of gathering financial resources from a number of individuals or organizations (Chalmeta et al., 2025; Hossain & Oparaocha, 2017) is able to transform the way in which art projects are produced (Marlett, 2015). Creative artists present their projects and ideas on platforms, using photographs, video materials and text, so as to invite the audience to support their initiatives. In other words, with the help of technology, crowdfunding puts together creative artists and the community, based on common values (Hossain & Oparaocha, 2017). Crowdfunding does not only represent a financing model but it also supports deeper audience involvement, by means of direct interaction between the artist and the community. The process results in fostering dialogue and cherishing common values. Some authors (Dalla Chiesa & Dekker, 2021) think that crowdfunded financing has a positive influence on the visibility of users, i.e. artists, and on their reputation.

The goal of the present paper is to review the most common models in artistic practice, their advantages and limitations, with a particular focus on the importance of the community for the success of the project. Relying on the overview of existing materials and empirical studies available so far, we consider how artists perceive the crowdfunding model and its long-term sustainability in an interdisciplinary context.

2. METHODOLOGY

In accordance with the research goals set above, PRISMA methodology has been used (*Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses*) as it enables a transparent and systematic approach to reviewing the relevant literature (Page et al., 2021). The analysis encompasses papers indexed in Web of Science (Core Collection) published between 2014 and 2025, looking into crowdfunded financing of

art projects. Key words used to search titles, abstracts, and full texts were *crowdfunding* and *art project*, which resulted in a list of 326 papers. This number was further reduced through the incorporation in our study of only those articles published in journals and conference proceedings, based on the assumption that these papers had undergone a stricter peer review process, resulting in their added scientific validity. Likewise, only literature in the English language was considered. After these additional criteria were applied, we ended up with 272 papers to analyze. In the next step we used a screening tool, aimed at the removal of duplicate texts, and also of papers that, in terms of the combination of titles, abstracts, and full texts, were not relevant to our research topic. The research sample comprised 20 papers, of which 18 were journal articles and 2 were contributions from conference proceedings.

3. RESULTS

In the studies that we have analyzed, authors consider various organizational and financial aspects of artistic activity, such as music, theatre, animation, and film, within a broader cultural and geographic context. The most commonly used platforms are Kickstarter, Tumbldug, and Voordekunst. These platforms can be viewed as financial tools, but also as instruments in a broader social context, i.e. as important elements in community buildup (Foà, 2019). Studies have encompassed various aspects of crowdfunding in art projects – from types of campaign creation and factors influencing their success, to financing models and the attitude of artists to crowdfunding strategies, all the way to a specific focus on the relationship between the creative artist and the audience donating funds.

Artists and donors do not start working together solely based on market principles. Rather, their cooperation is largely grounded in common values, such as social engagement, art promotion, and the buildup of collective identity (van den Hoogen, 2020).

3.1. Peculiarities of crowdfunding art projects

Our analysis of studies presented in Table 1 has enabled us to identify the main advantages and limitations of the crowdfunding model. The literature overview suggests that the authors have primarily studied the suitability of crowdfunding within the nonprofit sector.

Table 1: Papers identified in the systematic literature review

Author/year	Research goal	Methodology	Key findings
(Galuszka & Bystrov, 2014)	An analysis of crowdfunding as an alternative to the traditional financing of music production	A case study (the MegaTotal platform)	Project success largely depends on the number and frequency of donations and on active communication with the audience. Investors are often motivated by emotional connection with the participants, rather than profit.
(Foà, 2019)	A research of crowdfunding of art projects which specifically accentuate social and cultural values, as well as of marketing strategies and business models	A multiple case study	Crowdfunding campaigns pose risks and challenges, but also provide an opportunity for a specific model based on values, rather than product functionality.
(Wang, 2016)	A study of the potentials for a sustainable financing model based on the Kickstarter platform in music industry	Combined approach	Campaign success to a large extent depends on the already developed contact network. Social networks represent the primary channel for communicating with the audience.
(Alexiou et al., 2020)	A study of how the success of crowdfunding campaigns influences the overall fundraising for nonprofit organizations in performing arts	A quantitative data analysis (the Kickstarter platform)	Younger art organizations are more vulnerable to risks posed by crowdfunding, while for older organizations this financing method provides an additional fundraising opportunity.
(Villén Higuera et al., 2020)	An analysis of the influence of crowdfunding on project implementation in Chinese animated cartoon industry	A qualitative analysis (exploratory and descriptive methodology); case studies	Crowdfunding does not aim to fully cover production costs, but it represents an important project promotion strategy.
(Loriguillo-López, 2017)	Testing the possibilities for financing beyond the traditional framework, with a focus on crowdfunding Japanese animated cartoons	Multiple case studies	Although it cannot replace traditional investment, this model offers an opportunity to test the market and ideas; it also allows more creative freedom and more dynamic communication with the audience.

(Fanea-Ivanovici & Baber, 2021)	Suggesting a model to finance films and web TV shows that can be used in practice	A literature overview	The authors have developed a reward-based model consisting of nine phases which, in addition to involving the community to raise the funds, allows that the project idea be tested in a marked-based environment.
(D'Amato & Cassella, 2021)	A study of how various hidden mechanisms on crowdfunding platforms influence the success of the campaign.	A qualitative analysis (interview, discourse analysis)	The authors report that the platform inheres a selection process, which prioritizes projects that already exert social influence.
(Galuszka & Brzozowska, 2016)	Analysis of the concept of gift economy in the context of crowdfunding	A qualitative analysis (interview)	Artists offer gifts that require an amount of effort while donors' gifts are commercial in nature. The platform is not a mere market mechanism, but also provides room for enhancing the bond between the artist and the community.
(Guimarães & Maehle, 2025)	Analysis of crowdfunding aspects beyond the mere gathering of financial resources	A multiple case study	Crowdfunding is particularly relevant to young artists who aspire to position themselves in the market and win recognition, while more experienced artists use this tool in a better thought-out, strategic manner

3.2. Perceptions of participants in crowdfunded art projects

Table 2 presents the most important results of prior studies, with a particular focus on the attitudes of creative artists on the one hand, and donors (i.e. the audience) on the other. In their research, the authors have strived to understand the motivation for participating in crowdfunding campaigns. However, their results also suggest some limitations of this model, due to which the model itself is often perceived as just a temporary solution.

Table 2: Papers identified in the systematic literature review

Author/year	Research goal	Methodology	Key findings
(Dalla Chiesa & Dekker, 2021)	A study of the role and influence of crowdfunding on artist projects and careers	Inductive methodology and descriptive analyses (the data were collected by interviewing artists who had used the Voordekunst platform)	The artists cannot reach new audiences easily, which is why they mostly rely on the current network of acquaintances. Platforms enable them to establish professional distance.
(Galuszka & Brzozowska, 2017)	An analysis of the relationship between artists and donors within an equity/royalty based model on a crowdfunding platform.	A qualitative analysis (the data were obtained by interviewing platform users)	In parallel, crowdfunding helps empower artists, but may also result in their additional exploitation. Some negative effects have been identified: the model prioritizes early investors; in spite of the possibility of participation, creative cooperation often fails to materialize. However, the model still offers transparent communication.
(Fanea-Ivanovici, 2019)	Testing the attitudes of Romanian film industry workers on crowdfunding as a possible means of financing film projects	Combined approach (a survey and an interview)	Most film producers in Romania are not sufficiently familiar with this financing model, at least not enough to use it in practice. Some potentials of crowdfunding have been identified yet they require changes in the regulations.
(Dalla Chiesa, 2022)	A study of how artists perceive crowdfunding, with particular attention paid to the analysis of advantages and limitations	A qualitative analysis (an interview)	Most artists view crowdfunding as a temporary rather than long-term mechanism, to be used when other forms of financial support are unavailable. The model's lack of sustainability and insufficient distance from the audience have a negative influence on the artists' readiness to repeatedly participate in this practice. The model also poses additional risks to artists, since they often need to invest their own funds in campaigns.
(Davidson & Poor, 2015)	A research of the connection between social and psychological traits of artists and the crowdfunding process	A quantitative approach (questionnaire)	Results of the study suggest that more extroverted artists are more willing to use crowdfunding. Likewise, artists who already have a well-developed support network assess this model more positively.
(Kossecki & Świerczyńska-Kaczor, 2016)	An attempt to understand how crowdfunding works in Polish film industry, with a specific emphasis on the analysis of projects and attitudes of film professionals	Combined approach	Over 85% of participants positively assess the inclusion of sponsors in the production process. Identified obstacles involve an insufficient trust in crowdfunding and the lack of regulations. Participants who think that it is acceptable to share the profit with the donors comprise only one third of the sample.

(van den Hoogen, 2020)	A study of how various sets of values influence crowdfunding as a social phenomenon, on the example of the Netherlands	Combined approach	Personal connection with the artists and the broader societal impact of the project play an important part in attracting the audience. The majority of funds come from the already-existing, narrow circles of supporters. The market model most commonly works on the reward basis.
(Mollick & Nanda, 2016)	A comparison between the perception of theatre project financing by the audience and art experts	A quantitative method	Results suggest high correlation between the decisions made by the audience and by the experts. Some differences in terms of presentation have also been noted – materials based on multimedia and involving various rewards tend to better attract the audience, while the essence and content of the project tend to be better valued by the experts. However, there is no evidence that expert assessment positively influences project success – very often, it was the audience-selected projects that ended up being the most successful.
(Shneor et al., 2024)	An attempt to identify and provide deeper insight into artists' key decision-making factors regarding crowdfunding	A quantitative method (an online survey)	Artists already experienced in crowdfunding positively view the chance to use it again. If the environment encourages and supports the artist to undertake such action, the probably increases that the creative artist shall indeed take such a step.
(Boeuf et al., 2014)	An analysis of factors of success in a crowdfunding campaign involving theater projects, with a specific emphasis on the financial and symbolic rewards motivating donors	A quantitative analysis	Donors are not motivated by financial, but rather by symbolic rewards, such as their positive image and affiliation with the community. A need to broaden the networks has been identified, due to audience fatigue.

4. DISCUSSION

Crowdfunding is an innovative model which potentially offers several advantages, foremost the opportunity to diversify financing sources, which is crucially important for alternative projects, invisible to traditional donors (Fanea-Ivanovici & Baber, 2021; Galuszka & Bystrov, 2014; Loriguillo-López, 2017). The tool is essential for the visibility and promotion of as yet unestablished artists (Guimarães & Maehle, 2025). Further, crowdfunding provides an opportunity for direct artist-audience communication, fostering active audience participation (Foà, 2019; Galuszka & Bystrov, 2014; Villén Higuera et al., 2020). The equity-based and reward-based crowdfunding model additionally stimulates the stakeholders to participate in promotion and thus contribute to the project success, due to the fact that they either have a financial interest or symbolically feel affiliated with the project (Fanea-Ivanovici & Baber, 2021). Crowdfunding also provides a tool for preliminary market research, where the success of a campaign may signal more general audience interest. In this way, creative artists are in a position to test their ideas prior to more substantial investment (D'Amato & Cassella, 2021; Fanea-Ivanovici & Baber, 2021; Loriguillo-López, 2017). Research results also point out some limitations of the model, primarily the unpredictability of the project's outcomes (Galuszka & Bystrov, 2014) and impossibility to finance more ambitious or demanding endeavors (Galuszka & Bystrov, 2014; Loriguillo-López, 2017; Villén Higuera et al., 2020).

Dominant concepts in the analyzed literature revolve around two research methods: an analysis of the specifics of the practice of crowdfunding, with particular emphasis put on its organizational and financial aspects, and tests of creative artists' and donors' perceptions. For most artists, commercial success in this process goes hand in hand with numerous obstacles, which often limit the crowdfunding endeavors to a narrower, specialized audience (Dalla Chiesa & Dekker, 2021; Foà, 2019; Galuszka & Brzozowska, 2017). Artists claim that this model, which entails continued communication and constant involvement, often results in them being emotionally overwhelmed and exhausted. For this reason, they are not always ready to undertake new crowdfunding efforts (Dalla Chiesa, 2022; Fanea-Ivanovici, 2019; Kossecki & Świerczyńska-Kaczor, 2016). The lack of clear legislation and legal frameworks for donors often poses an additional obstacle, making their interest in investing in crowdfunded campaigns low (Fanea-Ivanovici, 2019; Kossecki & Świerczyńska-Kaczor, 2016). Studies comparing the audience and art experts have shown that the audience is ready to finance projects which experts would not prioritize, which does not mean that such projects are less successful (Mollick & Nanda, 2016). This opens up some room for defining crowdfunding as a mechanism of cultural diversification and correction of institutional mistakes.

5. CONCLUSION

The present research considers the phenomenon of crowdfunding in the context of art projects, with a specific emphasis on the predominant concepts and trends in the research literature. The goal of the study has been to provide a deeper insight into the most important theoretical and practical implications. The findings suggest that crowdfunding can significantly assist both early-career artists and alternative projects, in terms of fundraising and gathering support, which increases visibility and ensures independence from traditional institutional frameworks. In numerous studies, democratization is seen as an important element of crowdfunding (Foà, 2019; Guimarães & Maehle, 2025; Mollick & Nanda, 2016; van den Hoogen, 2020). It opens up room for social inclusion, pluralism in art, equal access to artistic materials, and participation in art productions. In spite of the increasing presence of the crowdfunding model, some studies (Fanea-Ivanovici, 2019; Kossecki & Świerczyńska-Kaczor, 2016) stress the lack of knowledge of its mechanisms and limited trust in its practical applicability.

The contribution of the paper can be found in its identification of dominant thematic wholes and key insights given in current literature, which can serve as the basis for future research. Since crowdfunding in the creative sector is a topic that has not yet been studied in Serbia, this paper can serve as additional inspiration for researchers to start working on the problem and enrich the relevant literature, but also for artists to potentially initiate the first models based on this practice. Our recommendation for future research is that empirical studies should be conducted in the Republic of Serbia, so as to better understand the attitudes to, familiarity with, and perception of the crowdfunding phenomenon among creative workers. Implications of such research can help support and develop crowdfunding platforms in Serbia, primarily oriented towards projects in the arts.

Limitations of the study pertain to the fact that we have considered only papers in the English language and that we have searched just one research database (WoS), which may have left out some relevant papers not detectable by our initial search criteria. Although the paper provides insight into the most important implications stemming from the relevant literature, the fact that we relied solely on secondary sources provides solid room for verifying our findings, especially in the local context.

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